

A new approach to assessing the content of natural hydrocarbons in soils

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In the context of the active development of oil and gas resources in Russia's northern territories, it is particularly important to develop scientifically sound approaches to assessing the natural background of hydrocarbons (HCs) in soils. Current standards do not consider natural climatic zoning, which often results in an inaccurate assessment of soil contamination in the Arctic and Subarctic regions. This article therefore proposes a new approach to ecological and hygienic assessment of natural HC content. This approach is based on determining background concentrations and identifying patterns of accumulation in the main soil types in the European north.

The study focused on Cryosols, Histosols, Fluvisols, Podzols, Retisols, Spodosols, Stagnosols and Umbrisols in the arctic and subarctic regions of the Komi Republic. Samples were collected using a route method that took landscape gradients from automorphic to hydromorphic conditions into account. HC concentrations were determined by measuring the fluorescence intensity of the hexane extract using a Fluorat-02-03M analyser. To systematise the results, a database and a map of the spatial distribution of natural HCs were created using GIS technologies (ArcView GIS 3.2a).

The results showed that organic soil horizons serve as a geochemical barrier and an integral indicator of aerotechnogenic loading, accumulating the highest concentrations of HCs. The content of HC depends on the granulometric composition of the parent rocks, the landscape's relief, and the type of pedogenesis. Maximum values are characteristic of accumulative and eluvial-accumulative landscapes (Retisols), while minimum values are characteristic of eluvial soils (Cryosols and Podzols). Profile differentiation is more pronounced in loamy soils (Retisols) and weaker in sandy soils (Podzols), where HCs are more uniformly distributed and leach more easily from podzolic horizons. Background HC concentration ranges vary widely, from 3.4 mg/kg in Haplic Cryosols to 40 mg/kg in Gleyic Stagnic Retisols.

As a key element of the new approach, threshold values are proposed for ecological and hygienic purposes, rather than average concentrations of HCs. These threshold values are defined as the upper 95th percentile for each soil type. This criterion takes natural fluctuations into account and excludes extreme values, ensuring a more accurate assessment of background HC content.

The resulting data and methodology can be used in engineering and environmental surveys and environmental impact assessments of the drilling, construction and operation of oil and gas facilities in high latitudes. They can also be used to improve standards for petroleum HC content, taking regional characteristics into account. The created database and map of natural HC distribution will form the basis for expanding the soil monitoring system and predicting pollution risks. In future, the methodology could be adapted for use with soils in other regions and supplemented with information on other classes of pollutants. This would enable a more comprehensive assessment of the resilience of soil ecosystems to human impact.

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